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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Assessing disadvantaged areas from the perspective of its residents

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Abstract – One of the main priorities of regional development policies is to catch up with disadvantaged areas. The disadvantages can be attributed to several reasons, but they pose the same economic and social challenges. The importance of supporting these regions for the development of the regions of Eastern Europe is unquestionable. Our study focuses on a disadvantaged settlement in Hungary. With our research, we sought the answer to how the people living here relate to their settlement. To answer this, we surveyed the opinions of the residents of the settlement with a questionnaire. Our results showed that the long-standing disadvantage created a depressive, passive, negative community. However, the lack of people actively involved in local development further hinders the movement of the settlement in a positive direction.

Keywords – regional development, disadvantaged areas, local society, quality of life, villages

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INTRODUCTION

The European Union spends a significant part of its activities and budget on reducing regional disparities, in particular rural areas, areas undergoing industrial change, and regions with severe and permanent natural or demographic handicaps. However, the enlargement of Central and Eastern Europe has led to an increase in regional disparities, with a large increase in lagging areas. The main characteristics of lagging, disadvantaged areas include general socio-economic backwardness; acute, persistently high unemployment; deepened structural crisis, the general decline of industry; the decline of agriculture, the shortcomings of the service sector; poor infrastructure, difficult access and isolation; persistent social crisis, declining quality of life and living conditions (segregation, deep poverty); deteriorating public safety.

Typical rural areas in Central and Eastern Europe are characterized by the modernization of agriculture, its crisis due to regime change, and its structural change in traditional industrial areas, which also poses a challenge to regional development. All this was accompanied by the intensification of unfavorable social processes, the deteriorating quality of life, and the emergence of non-viable rural communities.

This study focuses on the settlement of Gyöngyösoroszi in Heves County, Hungary, within the Gyöngyös District. The examined village is a beneficiary settlement in Hungary. The beginning of the decline of Gyöngyösoroszi can be traced back to the closure of the former ore mine there.

Our research aimed to assess the opinion and overall impression of the inhabitants of a disadvantaged small settlement. During the questionnaire survey conducted among the population, we looked for how much the residents like to live in Gyöngyösoroszi, how much they see perspective for the future generation, what they think about the atmosphere, what should be considered as strengths and weaknesses in the village life. Our further goal was to draw Gyöngyösoroszi's image profile based on the satisfaction values, which we also compared with the national level. In addition, we analyzed the attitudes of residents toward space by drawing mental maps.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The European Union (EU) will strengthen its economic, social, and territorial cohesion to promote its overall harmonious development. In particular, the EU aims to reduce disparities between the levels of development of its

various regions. Among the regions concerned, it shall pay particular attention to rural areas; areas affected by the industrial change, and regions with severe and permanent natural or demographic handicaps, such as the northernmost regions with extremely low population density, as well as islands, cross-border, and mountain areas.

The key to the European Union's cohesion policy for 2014-2020 was to focus on the priority of smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth (Farkas, 2021). Concerning its headline targets and 11 thematic objectives, it placed great emphasis on supporting less developed and transition regions (Hojcska and Szabó, 2021). More than 60% of the development resources of the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund (ESF), and the Cohesion Fund (CF) has been spent on the development of these regions. The eleven thematic objectives used in cohesion policy for the period 2014-2020 have been replaced by five policy objectives for the ERDF, the ESF, the Cohesion Fund, and the EMFF (European Maritime and Fisheries Fund):

- A more competitive and smarter Europe
- A greener, low-carbon transition to a net, zero-carbon economy
- A more connected Europe by increasing mobility
- A more social and inclusive Europe
- Bringing Europe closer to its citizens by promoting the sustainable and integrated development of all types of territory.

Cohesion policy continues to invest in all regions, still based on 3 categories (less developed, transitional, and more developed). In the red and orange regions shown in Figure 1, so-called county and local governments located in disadvantaged areas, as well as various enterprises and organizations are entitled to draw on and use resources that the territorial units in other regions do not have to compensate for their disadvantage (www.europa.eu).

The disadvantage mainly affects rural areas and their inhabitants (Bujdosó 2016). The total EU population is projected to grow by 2% between 2015 and 2030, while the rural population is expected to grow by only 0.6% (2.8 million) (Perpiñá et al., 2019). The largest increases are expected in Cyprus and Poland, and the largest decreases are likely to be in the Baltic region (Lithuania, Latvia) and Bulgaria.

Together with national trends, the regional rural population is generally higher in Eastern Europe (Romania, Hungary, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Poland) than in Western Europe. Between 2015 and 2030, a significant (> 10%) increase in the rural population in southern and north-eastern Spain is likely; Southeast Sweden, Finland, Belgium, Italy and northern Poland, Cyprus, and around most capitals (Bucharest, Budapest, Dublin, Madrid, Prague, Rome, Stockholm, Tallinn, Vienna, Warsaw, etc.). In contrast, a deep (> 10%) decline in the rural population is expected in northern Portugal, eastern Germany, and Hungary, and large areas in Sweden, Croatia, Greece, Romania, Lithuania, Latvia, and Bulgaria.

Figure 1. Development categorization of the regions of the European Union based on GDP per capita. (Source: Eurostat)

Dealing with disadvantaged areas has always been the focus of territorial policies and research on territorial inequalities. The backwardness and disadvantage of a region can usually be traced back to several reasons, it can be a natural endowment or a drift to the periphery as a result of some historical process or political decision, and these reasons usually appear as an economic disadvantage. The employment and social problems that emerge as a result of these factors and the exclusion from the circulation of the economy can increase the backwardness in a mutually reinforcing process, these areas are getting worse and worse in the absence of appropriate support and intervention (AKI, 2003). The general characteristic of disadvantaged areas is that a significant part of them has a low level of infrastructure provision, a low level of services, and a great lack of employment opportunities.

As a result, high unemployment and poor earnings are emerging. A general phenomenon is an emigration of the young generation from disadvantaged rural areas, which contributes to the development of an unfavorable aging structure in the long run (Káposzta et al., 2010). According to Jaszczak (2021), although areas, populations, and economic,

social, and administrative conditions vary from country to country, rural peripheral areas are characterized by many similarities, especially the most important development and economic problems, as well as infrastructure and transport, demographic and spatial changes. At the same time, the main development objective of EU rural policy is to support a significant proportion of the Community's rural population. Some findings from the literature on 6-7 disadvantaged areas in Central Europe (eg an article on other mining areas in Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Poland) would still be good on this topic.

The structural change in former mining areas is widely discussed in the literature (Eckart, 2003). After mining cessation and mine closure, most affected cities and regions face serious problems (Harfst et al. 2011). As their previous development depended on mining, its elimination is a huge challenge for local governments. Well-known problems in declining industrial regions, such as redundancies and rising unemployment, have emerged (Horváth 2003, 2005). The population's structure, social situation, and background have changed significantly. The original inhabitants, who worked mainly in agriculture, forestry, and related services, or possibly in traditional industries, were replaced by employees of mines, manufacturing, and related infrastructure. With the decline of mining, many have lost their jobs and find it difficult to find work in other fields due to their inadequate qualifications (Vaishar et al., 2010).

Several industrial areas in Eastern Europe have faced similar difficulties. Wirth et al. (2012) examine the adverse social, economic, and spatial effects of mine site closures and their solutions in Polish, Hungarian, Czech, and Slovenian case studies, among others. It is considered essential to validate the activating tools of the local community and increase community participation in city management. According to Wirth and Lintz (2007), European regions affected by mine closures are facing a fundamental structural crisis with three characteristic aspects: (1) environmental degradation of the landscape, (2) crisis in the region's overall economic base, and (3) high unemployment and related social problems.

The EU introduced 'community-led local development' (CLLD) in the 2014-2020 programming period, broadening significantly the scope of what was known as the 'LEADER approach (the bottom-up local development approach, systematized in successive LEADER periods). In the 2014-2020 funding period, it was relabeled as 'community-led local development' (CLLD) and was offered to all types of areas and contexts: rural, urban, and fisheries (Juma and Khademi-Vidra, 2019). It aims to increase employment and skills and social enterprise and ensures that local people are involved in developing projects, using resources in the area to address local challenges (Patkós 2018, Veselicz et al. 2022).

In the history of regional development in Hungary, 290/2014 (XI.26.) Government Decree entered into force on 1 January 2015 in connection with the delimitation of the beneficiary

areas. In classifying districts based on territorial development, the regulation takes into account a complex indicator formed from social and demographic, housing and living conditions, local economic and labor market, infrastructure, and environmental indicators (Szirmai 2015). Based on complex indicators, delimit the districts of the beneficiary, to be developed and to be developed with the complex program. Based on the results of the calculations, 53 districts were placed in the category of the beneficiary, 19 in the category to be developed, and 36 in the category to be developed with the complex program. 20% of the country's population lives in beneficiary districts, 15% in districts to be developed and 10% in districts to be developed with a complex program, calculated based on the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (KSH) data at the end of 2019.

On 1 January 2017 entered into force the Government Decree on the classification of the beneficiary settlements and the system of conditions for classification. The regulation also classifies the beneficiary settlements (1230) into two categories by calculating a complex indicator consisting of four groups of indicators: (1) settlements with significant unemployment, where the unemployment rate exceeds 1.75 times the national average, (2) socio-economic and infrastructural beneficiary settlements (Figure 2). Due to the difference between the newly applied district and the previously based micro-regional delimitation, some settlements lost their benefits. These were temporarily classified as beneficiaries (394).

Figure 2: The beneficiary settlements according to 105/2015. (IV. 23.) Government Decree
Source: Papp, 2018.

The organization of local society and the ability and efficiency of the use of available local resources are of great importance for the development of rural areas. A fundamental problem is that the development and development of lagging rural areas are seriously hampered by the disintegration and disintegration of local communities in rural society and the erosion of social structure (Jóna, 2013). As small settlements in disadvantaged areas have lost a significant part of their active, able, and willing residents for the community, and the proportion of the unmotivated, disappointed and pessimistic population is high (Bognár and Csizmady, 2005), the integration of local societies in lagging villages plays a significant role. community development activity and assistance.

The focus of our study is on a disadvantaged settlement, looking for the answer to how the people living here live their daily lives, subjectively how they judge their settlement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research area is the settlement of Gyöngyösoroszi in Heves county, Hungary, which we will discuss in more detail later. According to the before mentioned Government Decree, the settlement is considered to be a settlement benefiting from a socioeconomic and infrastructural point of view or suffering from significant unemployment. As a result of our previous study based on the complex indicators defined in the Government Decree, Gyöngyösoroszi graduated in the penultimate place in both years (2010 and 2016) in the development ranking of the settlements of the district (Szűcs and Káposzta, 2018).

We drew a mental map to get information about the respondents' questions about space use. We asked people living in different parts of the village to outline a map of the settlement on a blank piece of paper, marking each part of the village, fault lines, junctions, landmarks, and main routes.

To achieve our further objectives, we conducted a questionnaire survey among the residents of Gyöngyösoroszi between July and December 2019. The interview was conducted through personal interviews. As a result of the survey, we received 99 evaluable questionnaires so the sample was not representative. The questionnaire database was evaluated and analysed using SPSS 20.0. Cross-tabulation and analysis of variance methods were used to examine the relationships between different demographics and opinions about the settlement.

RESULTS

1. Presentation of the village from a regional point of view

Gyöngyösoroszi is a settlement of the Gyöngyös district in the Heves county of Northern Hungary, located at the bottom of the Mátra mountain (Figure 3). Its area: 2139 ha (with an administrative area, of which 75.37 ha is a municipally owned area, 140.5 ha with an inner area, 1996 ha with an outdoor area, and 2 ha with an enclosed garden), the population is 1546 people, which is a decrease of more than 4% since the turn of the millennium according to 2020 CSO (Hungarian Central Statistical Office) data (Figure 4.). The village is located in the western part of Heves county, in the Southern Mátra, 4 km NW of Gyöngyös, next to the Toka stream. Károlytáró is located in the inner part of the village, 7 km from the village. There are about 70 residential houses here.

Gyöngyösoroszi Ore Mine, the operation of which was suspended in 1986 due to uneconomical production. Twenty years later, with the closure, they wanted to solve a complex environmental and rehabilitation problem, and recultivation work began. The closure of the mine, which employs the majority of the local population, hurt the situation of the settlement, as many lost their jobs. Currently, a community-based institution, the House of Minerals, has been

implemented as a result of a private initiative. In addition, there were plans to set up a research facility to detect gravitational waves, and it was suggested that the area of the semi-mined ore mine could be a raw material exploration area again. In connection with the mine closure and reclamation works, and partly using its facilities, this was a unique opportunity, which was seized by a Hungarian ore exploration company (Földessy, 2016).

Figure 3. Location of Gyöngyösoroszi
Source: own editing

Its ore mining is of medieval origin, which ceased during the Turkish occupation. The factory of a precious metal mine was renovated in 1699. In 1945, the Hungarian state purchased the

Figure 4: Development of the natural reproduction and migration difference in Gyöngyösoroszi (2005-2020),
Source: own calculation

Previously, the main occupation of the population was grape production, as an excellent delicacy and wine grapes were grown in the hilly countryside of the village. Among the crops, wheat, oats, corn, and green fodder are the most significant. An Agricultural Producers' Cooperative, established in 1962, has not been operating since 1997 and has been liquidated. Many reclaimed and privately owned lands are cultivated individually, based on compensation or share.

According to the results of the 2011 census, the proportion of the population belonging to the Roma ethnic minority is 26.7%, which can be said to be significant. Their presence greatly contributes to the unfavourable economic and social situation of the settlement, they hinder the movement of the

active population, which is the main source of the problem in the village.

Figure 5 shows how the proportion of registered jobseekers in the settlement changes from the permanent population of working age to 2005-2020. At the district level, it can be stated that the value of the indicator follows the national values, however, the unfavourable situation of the village is visible. Especially in the period of the economic crisis starting from 2008, the most outstanding values can be observed, which later decreased, but at the end of the examined period (13.30%), they lag far behind the district (5.70%) and national values (4.57%).

Figure 5: Proportion of registered jobseekers in the permanent working age population in Gyöngyösoroszi (2005-2020). Source: own calculation

All in all, it can be said that due to the dissolution of economic entities, the proportion of the unemployed is currently above the national level, who either have a very low level of education or are over 50 years of age and no longer get a job due to their age. The conversation with the mayor revealed that the number of operating farms in the settlement is between 50-60, however, most of them operate as sole proprietorships or small limited companies, which can provide work for themselves or their family members at most. The largest employer is the Municipality of the village, which together with the kindergarten and school employs more than 40 people continuously. It is important to mention that in 2011 the government started the second public works program in Gyöngyösoroszi after the nearby Gyöngyöspata, but in addition, the employment of public workers is still ongoing.

We have census data on daily commuting, according to which 504 people were employed in the settlement in 2011, of whom 315 commuted, including 217 to Gyöngyös. Based on this, more people worked at the district centre than locally. The attraction of Gyöngyös has a strong impact on the settlement, its role is almost exclusive in terms of the provision of institutions at the city level.

2. Results of the questionnaire survey

Regarding the age distribution of the respondents, most (45.5%) of the oldest age group (over 51 years) answered our questions, followed by 31-50-year-olds with 31.3%, and finally, the youngest (18-30 year-olds) were represented in the sample. the lowest rate (23.2%). 54.1% of the respondents are women and 45.9% are men. Based on their marital status,

it can be said that nearly half of the individuals in the sample (48.5%) are married, 19.2% live in a cohabiting relationship, and 4% are divorced. Furthermore, 3.1% of them are single, typically the youngest age group, 4% are divorced, and 15.2% are widowed in the older age group.

Half of the respondents (53.1%) have a secondary education, 35.7% have a primary education and only 11.2% have a degree.

Examining the sample according to income conditions, it can be said that 23.5% of them receive less than HUF 50,000 net per month, and are students, unemployed, and public workers. 29.6% of them do not take home more than HUF 100,000 net per month. 23.5% of them marked the category 100,001 - 150,000 HUF, and 16% of them the above (HUF 150,001 - 200,000). In the two largest income categories (above HUF 200,001 - 250,000 and HUF 250,001), respondents were equally represented (3.7%).

The presentation of the demographic characteristics of the sample is also important from the point of view that we can examine the significant differences in the assessment and opinions of the settlement based on these variables. However, such correlations were found in only a few cases, which we will discuss later.

In the questionnaire, we asked the respondents to mark on the Likert scale from 1 to 5 the question of how much they like to live in the settlement. Most (28.6%) are indifferent to this question, circling the value of 3. Overall, the respondents do not feel good in Gyöngyösoroszi, 23.1% of them marked the worst value of 1, and another 24.2% marked the better category. A positive response (grades 4 and 5) was given to 22 of the 99 people, which is somewhat reassuring. Next, in connection with this question, we asked the respondents to explain what they like about the settlement. In a large proportion, the answer was simply worded "nothing". At the same time, we received a noteworthy proportion of responses related to the landscape, the fresh air, and the proximity of the Mátra. In addition, many also mentioned the proximity of the city, Gyöngyös.

In the survey, we were also curious about the symbols (objects, living things, actions, people, etc.) that remind residents of the settlement. As a result, the respondents typically identify their settlement with the mine, the Mátra, the minerals, and the Roma minority.

With the questionnaire, we examined the overall picture and atmosphere of the settlement. During the survey, it turned out that the mood of Gyöngyösoroszi, according to the respondents, is negative. A quarter of respondents found their village depressing. In addition, 20% consider it tense, 18% disgusted, and 17% unanimous. Positive indicators such as calm, cheerful, and cozy marking did not even reach 10%. According to the respondents, the strength that distinguishes Gyöngyösoroszi from the other settlements of Hungary is the most unique landscape values (47%) and natural formations (45.8%). According to them, the cultural-historical values are

less of a strength of the village (7.2%). We then assessed what the people of Gyöngyösoroszi consider to be the weaknesses of the settlement. Most of the nominations, which came from three-quarters of those surveyed, went to public safety. In addition, more than half of them (57 people) consider the lack of jobs and almost half of them (43 people) the entertainment opportunities for young people to be the weak points of the village. The problem with keeping young people in place is that one-third of the respondents also marked the perspective provided for young people as an answer to this question. Related to this are the results of the answers to the question of what improvements are considered most important in the next 5 years, as the greatest proportions have been formulated to improve public safety, create jobs, renovate roads and address Roma issues.

Our sense of comfort is greatly influenced by the conditions in which we live our daily lives, covering our own space here. Overall, the locals surveyed consider the condition of their own flat/house to be good, with only 13 people marking the two worst categories on this scale on a 5-point scale. Furthermore, a crosstab confirmed the relationship between housing status and educational attainment (Pearson's chi-square value of 75.327, $\alpha = 0.000$) and income status (Pearson's chi-square value of 112.432, $\alpha = 0.000$). The higher the level of education and income of the respondent, the better he/she considers his / her own home. However, this connection is not surprising, as there are more opportunities for those living in a better financial situation to renovate their homes and shape them according to their own needs.

With the help of an open question during the survey, we also examined the opinion of the residents about whether it is possible to keep young people aged 0-18 living in the settlement here after leaving the school system. The assessment of this is not positive either, as only 7 of the respondents believed that the village could have a perspective for young people. It is important to note that this question was tied to nationality by the respondents, according to others, only the minority can be residents of Gyöngyösoroszi in the future. If we compare these opinions with the development of the migration balance described earlier, there may be a serious threat to the unfavourable composition of the population and the intensification of depopulation processes in the future.

This problem was reinforced by the outcome of our next question. Respondents rated on a scale of 1 to 5 how attractive the settlement was. The results revealed that the village was not considered liveable for any of the target groups we identified. Based on the values in Figure 6, it can be seen that Gyöngyösoroszi is not recommended as a destination for those looking for a new home, for young married people, for entrepreneurs and investors, or even for tourists.

In the analysis of variance, we found a significant difference between the mean values of the responses ($F = 3.334$, $\alpha = 0.040$) based on the respondents' educational attainment, suggesting that those with higher education consider the local community to be more exploited (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Evaluation of the attractiveness of the settlement (arithmetic average)

Source: Own calculation based on a questionnaire survey

Figure 7. Evaluation of the local community by educational attainment (arithmetic mean)

Source: Own calculation based on a questionnaire survey

We drew the image profile of Hungary and Gyöngyösoroszi based on the average values by evaluating economic, social, cultural, and environmental factors from 1 to 5. Based on Figure 8, it can be stated that the situation of the country is considered to be better by the respondents than their settlement, but in several cases, the settlement closely follows domestic values. For each of the economic factors, the national values exceed the settlement values. Only the accessibility of Hungary, the existence of successful businesses, shopping opportunities, and development was judged to be better than average, and Gyöngyösoroszi did not reach the triple value in any respect. In addition to economic factors, social and cultural aspects are not included with better results based on average values, however, gastronomic traditions are considered to be better in the settlement than at the national level. The best judgments were made among the

environmental factors, as a positive, it can be said that the climate of the village is felt by the respondents better than in Hungary. The landscape achieved the best average value at both the domestic (4.11) and settlement (3.91) levels. Overall, the image profile of both territorial levels shows an unfavorable picture, the respondents are the least satisfied with the development and public safety of the village.

Figure 8. Image profile of Hungary and Gyöngyösoroszi
 Source: Own calculation based on a questionnaire survey

3. The mental map of local residence

We drew a mental map to get information about the respondents' questions about space use. We asked people living in different parts of the village to outline a map of the settlement on a blank piece of paper, marking each part of the village, fault lines, junctions, landmarks, and main routes

Mental or cognitive mapping is the product of a series of psychological processes that register, code, store, then call to mind and decode all information on our everyday spatial environment. Mental mapping is a commonly used method in sociology (Pap 2019, Kaisto-Wells 2021).

Based on the representations of the respondents, the following common features emerged from the mental map of the village:

- The primary school, the House of Culture, the bus stop, the Savings Cooperative, the post office, and the church appear as hubs in the life of Gyöngyösoroszi. In addition, it is important to mention that residences appeared very often on mental maps, suggesting that the residential function is primary among respondents. Furthermore, in almost all cases, the bus stop was depicted, which assumes frequent commuting. In general, it can be said that the nodes are the same in the minds of the respondents, ie everyone drew the same institution, or service place, regardless of which part of the settlement they live in.

- The landmarks of the villagers are the primary school, the kindergarten, the House of Culture, the post office, and the church. In addition, one-third of the respondents, who came from the older age group, also indicated the cemetery as an important reference point, which can be explained by the fact that due to their age, they visit the graves of several of their relatives more often.

- Examining the fault lines at the social level, based on the drawings of the respondents, it can be said that they are clearly based on ethnicity, as the part of the settlement inhabited by Roma was most often displayed. The majority of respondents marked the reservoir above the village as a natural fault line.

- It is characteristic of the marking of the routes that the responding villagers marked the streets and institutions with more marked lines that are connected to their living spaces. In addition, interviewees marked their streets more markedly. An important result is that the rate of mention of the road leading to Gyöngyös is very high, based on which the dependence on the city appears.

The proportions of the hand-drawn maps differed from reality, as the spaces and routes considered important by the respondents appeared larger, and the areas that were less important to them sometimes disappeared.

It is also worth noting that more than half of the conversations during the mapping process mentioned stereotypes about certain parts of the settlement, which meant streets inhabited by Roma.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Overall, its population paints a negative image of the examined village, it can be characterized by indifference, depression, and indifference, the residents here do not feel good in their settlement. Only natural geographical factors and proximity to the district center were formulated as values, pointing to a high degree of dependence on the city. The biggest problems are the situation of public security, the high Roma population, and the high level of unemployment.

The unfavorable situation in Gyöngyösoroszi can be traced back to the closure of the mine since after that the status of the settlement deteriorated, and as a result of the selective emigration, the proportion of Roma started to increase. The

intervention plans formulated at the central level were not implemented, due to which it was not possible to start reversing the negative processes.

Further deterioration in the demographic composition of the population living here will also contribute to making the disadvantages permanent. Population conditions can affect the viability of an area in several ways. An aging age structure can be a major maintenance burden for local governments and the working-age population, hampering the economic renewal of an area. Emigration, which usually affects the working-age population, is again only an unfavorable process for economic recovery. In the lagging areas, therefore, catching up cannot be solved by economic policy instruments alone, instead, a complex policy aimed at creating a sustainable, viable local society can achieve results (Némethy, 2021). Population processes are therefore not only a consequence of economic developments but also influence them, reinforcing existing trends.

REFERENCES

- 290/2014. (XI.26.) Government Decree: 290/2014. (XI.26.) Government Decree on the classification of beneficiary districts
- 105/2015. (IV. 23.) Government Decree: 105/2015. (IV. 23.) on the classification of the beneficiary settlements and the system of conditions for the classification
- AKI (2003). Agricultural employment in disadvantaged areas - Practical application of EU opportunities. Issue 4, Budapest, ISBN 963 491 452 7 p.104.
- Beluszky P. (2000). The development of the Hungarian settlement system (in Hungarian). Enyedi Gy., ed. The settlement environment of Hungary. 465 p. Budapest: Hungarian Academy of Sciences, pp. 9–76.
- Bujdosó Z. (2016). The relationship between tourism and regional development in Hungary. In: Kókai, S (ed.) The changing world XXI. challenges of the 20th century: study volume in honor of the 70th birthday of Prof. Dr. Hanusz Árpád Nyíregyháza, Hungary: Institute of Tourism and Geography of Nyíregyháza University, pp. 63-76
- Bognár L., Csizmady A. (2005). The situation of villages - the public mood in villages. (in Hungarian) In. László Bognár, Adrienne Csizmady, Pál Tamás and Tímea Tibori (eds.): Perceptions of the Nation - Village Policies. New Mandate Publishing House - MTA SZKI, Budapest, 36-41. p.
- Eckart, K. (2003). Social, economic, and cultural aspects in the dynamic changing process of old industrial regions. Ruhr District (Germany), Upper Silesia (Poland), Ostrava Region (Czech Republic), Münster: LIT Verlag
- Farkas, T. (2021). The Role of the Social Capital in Rural Development. Case Study Analysis of Village Research Camps in Romania and Hungary" European Countryside, 13(3) 584-598.
- DOI: [10.2478/euco-2021-0033](https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2021-0033)
- Földessy J. (2016). Resuscitation experiments in ore exploration in Mátra. (in Hungarian) *Geoda*, 16(2), 35-40.
- Gy. Jóna (2013). Conceptual approaches to territorial capital. *Tér és Társadalom* 17(1), 30-51.
DOI: [10.17649/TET.27.1.2449](https://doi.org/10.17649/TET.27.1.2449)
- Harfst, J. - Wirth, P. (2011). Structural change in former mining regions: problems, potentials, and capacities in multi-level-governance systems. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 2011(14), 167–176.
DOI: [10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.03.033](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.03.033)
- Hojcska, A.E., Szabó, Z. (2021). Investigating Natural Treatment Factors and Inequalities of Medicinal Water Institutions in the Aspect of Tourism in Hungary. *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 36(2spl), 555–562.
DOI: [10.30892/gtg.362spl01-683](https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.362spl01-683)
- Horváth, G. (2003). Landscape and human effect: recent changes in the Medves Area, North (Hungary). In: Vaishar, A., Zapletalová, J.&Munzar, J., eds. Regional geography and its applications. Frenštát pod Radhoštěm, pp. 60–65.
- Horváth, G. (2005). Problems of the transition in the Medves Area (North Hungary). In: Ilić, M., ed. Problemi region along razvoja Hrvatske i susjednih zemalja/Regional development problems in Croatia and neighboring countries. Zagreb, pp. 125–133
- Jaszczak A. & Vaznoniene G. & Kristianova K. & Atkociuniene V. (2021). Social and Spatial Relation Between Small Towns and Villages in Peripheral Regions: Evidence from Lithuania, Poland, and Slovakia. *European Countryside* 13(2), 242-266.
DOI: [10.2478/euco-2021-0017](https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2021-0017)
- Juma L.O., Khademi-Vidra A. (2019). Community-Based Tourism and Sustainable Development of Rural Regions in Kenya; Perceptions of the Citizenry. *Sustainability*. 11(17):4733.
DOI: [10.3390/su11174733](https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174733)
- Kaisto, V., Wells, C. (2021). Mental Mapping as a Method for Studying Borders and Bordering in Young People's Territorial Identifications, *Journal of Borderlands Studies*, 36(2), 259-279,
DOI: [10.1080/08865655.2020.1719864](https://doi.org/10.1080/08865655.2020.1719864)
- Káposzta J., Nagy H., Kollár K. (2010). Settlement structural and employment characteristics of the most disadvantaged micro-regions of Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén and Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg counties in the period since EU accession, (in Hungarian) *Területi Statisztika* 13(6), 641-658.
- Mátyás, Sz. (2021). Talent geography analyzes in the Carpathian Basin (In Hungarian) *Területi Statisztika* 61 (4) 466-502

Nemethy, S. (2021). New, regenerative approaches to sustainability: Redefining ecosystem functions, environmental management, and heritage conservation. *Ecocycles*, 7(2), 86–91.

DOI: [10.19040/ecocycles.v7i2.212](https://doi.org/10.19040/ecocycles.v7i2.212)

Patkós, Cs. (2018). Specialities in the Institutionalisation of Hungarian Leader Local Action Groups European Countryside (10)1, 89-106.

DOI: [10.2478/euco-2018-0006](https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2018-0006)

Papp, S. (2018). Possibilities of demarcating disadvantaged areas. (In Hungarian) In: *Eötvözet VI.: The Eötvös József Collegium and the Eötvös Loránd College VI. presentations at its joint conference. Acta Szegediensia Collegii de Rolando Eötvös nominati* (6). SZTE Eötvös Loránd College, Szeged, pp. 149-160.

Pap V. (2019). Researching the spirit of place. Mental mapping on Sziget festival *Corvinus Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 10(1) 56-69,

DOI: [10.14267/CJSSP.2019.1.6](https://doi.org/10.14267/CJSSP.2019.1.6)

Perpiñá, CC, Barranco, R., Kavalov, B., Jacobs-Crisioni, C., Silva, F., Baranzelli, C., Lavalle, C., Diogo, V. (2019). Territorial Facts and Trends in the EU Rural Areas within 2015-2030. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg,

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2760/525571>

Petrov K. (2021). The Regional Development of the Rural Areas in Bulgaria and the Support of the European Union. *European Countryside* 13(1), 208-221.

DOI: [10.2478/euco-2021-0012](https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2021-0012)

Szirmai, A. (2015). *Socio-Economic Development*. 2nd edn. Cambridge University Press. Available at:

<https://www.perlego.com/book/1400022/socioeconomic-development-pdf> (Accessed: 14 October 2022).

Szűcs A., Káposzta J. (2018). Complex development ranking and dynamics of the settlements of Gyöngyös district (in Hungarian) *Területi Statisztika* 58 (5), 489–504.

DOI: [10.15196/TSS580503](https://doi.org/10.15196/TSS580503)

Vaishar, A., Štátná, M., Lipovská, Z. (2010). Possibilities for development of regions after mining: restoration of the rural environment in the Czech-Saxon borderland. In: *Linking competitiveness with equity and sustainability: new ideas for the socio-economic development of rural areas*. ERDN Warszawa, pp. 97-112.

Veselicz, A., Péntes, J., Patkós, Cs. (2022). Decentralized Funding Activities of the Leader Local Action Groups of the North Hungarian Region from a Governance Point of View *European Countryside* 14(2), 217-231.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2022-0011>

Wirth, P., Lintz, G. (2007). Strategies of Rehabilitation and Development in European Mining Regions. In *Good (Best) Practice Cases in Regional Development after Mining and Industry*. Grazer Schriften der Geographie und Raumforschung. Universität Graz, pp. 75-85

Wirth, P., Mali, B., Fischer, W. ed. (2012). *Post-Mining Regions in Central Europe. Problems, Potentials, Possibilities*. Oecom Verlag, München, 274 p.

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